

Simulation of SINR and CQI-Based Handover Mechanism in LTE Networks using Simu5G

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Abstract— In LTE networks, the handover mechanism is essential for maintaining Quality of Service (QoS) and guaranteeing uninterrupted connectivity, particularly in high-mobility scenarios. This project uses the OMNeT++, INET, and Simu5G frameworks to simulate and analyse handover performance using SINR (Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio) and CQI (Channel Quality Indicator) metrics in a controlled LTE environment. In order to facilitate dynamic handover, the study starts by building a network with several eNodeBs and mobile user equipment (UEs), integrating X2 interface signalling. By adding a custom load-aware handover logic that takes into account the current user load on cells, the default SINR-based handover triggering is further enhanced. Key metrics like throughput, delay, packet loss, and handover success rate under various mobility conditions are highlighted in the simulation results. Vector traces and live handover tracking are used to confirm the improved logic's efficacy. The work offers insights into enhancing handover strategies while addressing configuration and implementation issues. In addition to validating standard LTE procedures, this study investigates improvements that can be applied to 5G transition networks that still rely on LTE infrastructures by simulating realistic handover behaviour. The results aid in the creation of adaptive handover algorithms appropriate for heterogeneous mobile networks of the future.

Keywords— SINR, CQI, Simu5G, OMNeT++, load-aware mobility, X2 signalling, QoS, and LTE handover Cellular networks Optimisation of handover.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mobile communication has advanced quickly over the last few decades, moving from first-generation analogue systems to 5G's incredibly dependable low-latency networks. Ensuring smooth user connectivity while on the go is one of the major challenges in mobile network operation. This is controlled by the handover procedure, which involves the uninterrupted transfer of an active session between base stations. For real-time services like voice-over-IP, video conferencing, and vehicle communication systems, efficient handover is especially crucial [14]. Handovers are typically difficult and network-controlled in LTE (Long Term Evolution) networks. Although they make signalling simpler, in high-mobility situations they may experience higher packet loss, higher latency, and service degradation. In conventional systems, the choice to hand over is determined by factors like the Channel Quality Indicator (CQI), Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio [15]. Legacy handover algorithms are now subject to additional limitations as a result of the explosion in data demand, user growth, and network densification. More intelligent, context-aware mobility management is required in heterogeneous networks, which comprise Wi-Fi hotspots, femtocells, small cells, and macro cell [16]. Current studies demonstrate how AI and machine learning methods can enhance quality of experience (QoE), reduce ping-pong effects, and increase handover accuracy. These methods use data-driven forecasts of user mobility and network conditions to adjust handover parameters on the fly [17]. Simulation tools such as Simu5G and OMNeT++ offer useful platforms for assessing these mechanisms in controlled settings. The goal of this project is to use SINR and CQI-based logic in LTE networks to simulate

handover events while incorporating a load-aware decision mechanism. The outcomes of the simulation shed light on how to best manage mobility in both early 5G scenarios and existing LTE deployments, where backward compatibility is crucial.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Handover involves the movement of an in progress call or data session between two cells without traffic break. In cellular networks it is of paramount importance, particularly in high-mobility networks. The traditional LTE handover follows signal-strength and predetermined threshold-based handover strategy, but the newer approaches are dynamically, intelligent [8]. More recent studies show that handover decision can be enhanced with mobility prediction, traffic load, and users behavior. The AI/ML techniques including deep learning, Q-learning, and decision trees forecast the best times to handover, mitigate the ping-pong effects, and improve the user experience by studying the past data and radio conditions [9].

Other studies compare the handover algorithms at various speeds of users, types of traffic (such as VoIP, video, etc.) and conditions (urban, rural, etc.). These algorithms can be simulated and tested with the help of such tools as OMNeT++, NS-3, MATLAB [10]. Riaz et al. suggested a data-driven optimization with MLP based model to optimize handover parameters (HOM, TTT) dynamically. Their strategy has up to 90 percent less HOF, HOR, HOPP, and RLF by taking into account parameters like RLF, RSRP, SINR, speed, and load due to increased adaptability to dense 5G HetNets [11].

Such studies have a direct influence on my project since they lead to an understanding of how a handover can be changed beyond the fixed thresholds of decisions. Based on this, in my OMNeT++, INET and Simu5G projects I do observing default SINR-based handovers, and testing load balanced logic. I use the wisdom of the latest studies on dynamic parameter adjustment and active decision-making as a basis of my ideas on how to enhance the performance of handovers in a simulated network of LTE and 5G

III. METHODOLOGY

This project's methodology uses OMNeT++, INET, and Simu5G to implement and assess a load-balanced handover mechanism in a simulated LTE network. To accomplish the project's goals, the following actions were taken in a methodical manner.

A. Configuration for the Simulation

INET 4.x and Simu5G 1.2.2 served as the foundational simulation frameworks for the simulation, which was created in OMNeT++ 6.x. A server serves as the traffic source, two eNodeBs (eNodeB1 and eNodeB2), a packet gateway (PGW) and a router connect to the core network, and numerous UEs (user equipment) are dispersed and mobile within the coverage area of both eNodeBs.

B. Configuration of Mobility and Traffic

To move within a constraint area that covers both cells, each UE was set up with LinearMobility. At first, every UE was connected to eNodeB1, but under specific circumstances, handovers were permitted during the simulation. VoIPSender and VoIPReceiver apps were used to create downlink traffic from the server to every UE.

C. Measurement Gathering

The simulation periodically gathers the following information for each UE:

- The cell load (i.e., the number of UEs presently connected to each eNodeB);
- The SINR (Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio) from the serving eNodeB.

These measurements are kept in monitoring vectors and are updated continuously

D. Handover Decision Logic

The decision process for each UE follows the flow illustrated in the project flowchart:

Figure 1: Flowchart illustrating the load-balancing and handover decision process.

i. Start Simulation:

- Each UE begins collecting SINR and cell load information.

ii. Evaluate SINR:

- If SINR of the current serving eNodeB is above a defined threshold, proceed to load evaluation.
- If not, compare SINR with neighboring eNodeBs.

- iii. Load Check:
 - If the serving eNodeB's load exceeds a predefined maximum, trigger a handover to the least-loaded neighboring eNodeB.
 - If not, continue with the current eNodeB and keep monitoring.
- iv. Neighbor SINR Comparison:
 - If a neighboring eNodeB has better SINR, trigger a handover to that cell.
 - Otherwise, remain connected and continue monitoring.

Figure 1 shows the step-by-step decision process implemented in this project. The process begins by collecting SINR and load metrics from all UEs. If the current serving cell's SINR is acceptable, the system then evaluates its load. When the load crosses a threshold, a handover is triggered toward the least-loaded neighboring cell. If the SINR of a neighboring eNodeB is significantly better than that of the current eNodeB, a handover is also triggered to maintain connection quality. Otherwise, the UE continues with its current serving cell while periodically monitoring network conditions. This flow ensures dynamic load balancing and efficient handover management.

E. Handover Execution

Once a handover decision is made, the simulation invokes the `sendHandoverCommand()` method via the X2 interface between eNodeBs. The UE's serving cell information is updated, and data forwarding continues seamlessly from the new eNodeB.

F. Continuous Monitoring

After each handover, the UE continues monitoring SINR and load, enabling dynamic balancing between cells as UEs move through the network.

G. Data Collection and Analysis

The simulation records:

- Number of active UEs per eNodeB (`numActiveUEsVector`)
- SINR values over time
- Resource block usage.

These outputs are analyzed to verify that load balancing and SINR-based handover function as expected, improving overall network efficiency and user experience.

IV. RESULTS

- i. Initial UEs connect to eNodeB1.
- ii. As mobility changes SINR, handover occurs to eNodeB2.
- iii. Load-aware handover balances users between cells.
- iv. Verified using X2 logs, vector traces, and visual session tracking.

Figure 2: Initial network setup showing multiple UEs and eNodeBs.

Initial network setup Figure 2 – Initial network setup showing multiple UEs and eNodeBs This figure illustrates the initial topology configured in the OMNeT++ simulation environment. Two eNodeBs are placed at fixed positions, and multiple UEs are scattered within their coverage area. This layout sets the stage for mobility and handover events during the simulation.

Figure 3: Handover control triggered via X2 interface.

Hand over via X2 interface This figure 3 shows internal signaling activity between eNodeBs through the X2 interface. It highlights how handover control commands are exchanged, enabling a seamless transfer of UEs while maintaining active sessions.

Figure 4: Live simulation output showing packet feedback and handover events.

Live simulation output The final figure displays live vector and scalar feedback from the simulation, including packet traces and event logs. It confirms that handover events occurred successfully and load balancing logic distributed UEs across available eNodeBs.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The proposed project can effectively prove the simulation of SINR CQI supported handover in load balancing LTE network that uses OMNeT++ 6.1, INET 4.5.4, and Simu5G 1.2.2. The simulation uses the configuration of several eNodeBs and UEs mobile to demonstrate the handover performed by users who first attach themselves to one cell and subsequently update the connection to another cell depending on the real-time SINR situation. Under the presence of the additional load-balancing criterion, the presence of the overloaded cell leads to a distribution of the UEs between the available eNodeBs and therefore, the network resource utilisation is better used. OMNeT++ simulation results confirmed using X2 signaling logs, tracing the vectors, and visual analysis indicates the efficiency of the combination of traditional SINR/CQI-based handover and adaptive load-balancing strategies. The given work is a great background to further enhancement which includes: Classification of handovers with machine learning, Energy efficiency study, Scaling out to high density small-cells or 5G. In general, the given project illustrates the feasible solution to the improvement of the handover management in the LTE networks and reveals how smart decisions can deepen the performance in the new mobile networks.

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